

COFFEE SYMPHONY: EXAMINING THE INFLUENCE OF BACKGROUND MUSIC ON NATIVE COFFEE FLAVOR

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to investigate the impact of background music on the taste perception of native coffee. The study involved 30 coffee drinkers from the faculty and staff of West Visayas State University as participants. Different music genres, including classical, ballad, jazz, and pop, were utilized during the study conducted throughout the school year 2023-2024. Participants were selected using the purposive sampling method, and the research employed a quasi-experimental design with treatments replicated three times. A researcher-made sensory evaluation score sheet was used to collect data for the study, and statistical analysis involved mean, standard deviation, and t-tests, with an alpha level of .05 used as the criterion for accepting or rejecting the null hypothesis. Statistical computations were conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The results indicated that, before exposure to background music, participants perceived the taste of brewed native coffee as moderately subtle, regardless of whether they were considered as a whole group or classified by gender and age. Interestingly, females found the taste to be very subtle. When exposed to different types of background music, participants generally found the taste of brewed native coffee to be moderately subtle, except for older individuals exposed to classical music and all participants exposed to ballad music, who found the taste to be very subtle. Prior to exposure to background music, all participants perceived the aroma of native coffee as very nutty. When exposed to different types of background music, most participants found the aroma to be very subtle, with exceptions noted for females exposed to classical music and males exposed to jazz music, who rated the aroma as moderately nutty. No significant differences were observed in the taste and aroma of native coffee among participants when classified by gender and age. Overall, this study sheds light on the

influence of background music on the taste and aroma perception of brewed native coffee, providing valuable insights into sensory experiences and preferences among coffee drinkers.

Keywords: *Background Music Impact, Native Coffee Study, Music Genres Effect, Sensory evaluation, Statistical Analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

The impact of music on the brain's organization and functions is profound, influenced by its melody and rhythm. Research by Levitin (2006) has shown that music has a direct influence on the brain's serotonin levels. Serotonin, a key neurotransmitter facilitating the transmission of nerve signals, plays a pivotal role in sustaining feelings of joy and contentment (Harmer, 2008). Low levels of serotonin have been linked to conditions like depression, emphasizing the importance of this hormone in emotional well-being (Nestler et al., 2002). Noteworthy is the brain's release of serotonin in response to positive stimuli - be it admiring art, savoring delightful scents, experiencing intense sensations, enjoying delectable food, or being enchanted by captivating music, all triggering the release of serotonin, amplifying pleasurable emotions.

The physical effects of music on the body are diverse, ranging from heightened molecular energy levels and modulation of muscle tone to rhythmic impacts on heart rate, metabolic changes, stress reduction, revitalization of energy, emotional release, and stimulation of creativity and cognition. Studies by Thaut (2005) and Blood et al. (1999) have demonstrated the profound impact of music on heart rate and stress reduction. Renowned researcher Dr. Roy J. Paget suggests that classical and baroque music (from 1750 to around 1850) evoke a consistent response from the body and brain. This could be attributed to the synchronization between classical music's rhythm (typically 60 beats per minute) and pitch with human brainwave patterns, fostering a harmonious interaction.

Coffee stands as a beloved beverage worldwide, cherished for its invigorating properties and widespread consumption. Each morning, countless individuals depend on their daily dose of coffee to kickstart their day, drawn to its unique appeal for various personal reasons. Across the United States and beyond, coffee symbolizes hospitality, often shared among friends and family, fostering engaging conversations with its alluring aroma and rich flavor. Coffee has become synonymous with camaraderie and relaxation, intertwining itself with social bonds and moments of tranquility.

Background music holds significance in the realm of coffee consumption, evident in the prevalence of musical ambiance in many coffee establishments. Drawing inspiration from Adrian North's research on the influence of background music on the taste of wine, this study seeks to explore the potential impact of background music on the perception and experience of coffee taste.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to determine the effect of background music on the taste of native coffee.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the taste of native coffee before the coffee drinkers are exposed to background music and when they are taken as an entire group and classified according to gender and age?
2. What is the taste of native coffee after the coffee drinkers were exposed to (a) classical music, (b) ballad music, (c) jazz music, (d) pop music, and when they are taken as an entire group and classified according to gender and age?
3. What is the aroma of native coffee before the coffee drinkers are exposed to background music and when they are taken as an entire group and classified according to gender and age?
4. What is the aroma of native coffee after coffee drinkers are exposed to (a) classical music, (b) ballad music, (c) jazz music, (d) pop music, and when they are taken as an entire group and classified according to gender and age?
5. Are there significant differences in taste of native coffee before the coffee drinkers are exposed to background music when they are classified according gender and age?
6. Are there significant differences in taste of native coffee after coffee drinkers are exposed to (a) classical music, (b) ballad music, (c) jazz music, (d) pop music, when they are classified according to gender and age?
7. Are there significant differences in aroma of native coffee before coffee drinkers were exposed to background music when they are classified according gender and age?
8. Are there significant differences in aroma of native coffee after the coffee drinkers were exposed to (a) classical music, (b) ballad music, (c) jazz music, (d) pop music, when they are classified according to gender and age?

Hypotheses:

In view of the preceding problems, the following hypothesis are advanced:

1. There are no significant differences in taste of native coffee before the coffee drinkers were exposed to background music when they are classified according to gender and age.
2. There are no significant differences in taste of native coffee after coffee drinkers were exposed to (a) classical music, (b) ballad music, (c) jazz music, (d) pop music, when they are classified according to gender and age.
3. There are no significant differences in the aroma of native coffee before the coffee drinkers were exposed to background music and when are they classified according to gender and age.

4. There are no significant differences in the aroma of native coffee after the coffee drinkers were exposed to (a) classical music, (b) ballad music, (c) jazz music, and (d) pop music, when they are classified according to gender and age.

METHODOLOGY

This experimental method of research was used in the study. Gay (1976) describes this method as the method of difference in which the independent variable also referred to as the experimental variable.

In this study, the antecedent variables were the personal factors such as gender and age; the process variables were the different types of background music which include the; classical, ballad, jazz and pop music; and the criterion variables were the taste and aroma.

The participants of the study were 30 faculty and staff of West Visayas State University who were identified as coffee drinkers. Purposive samplings were used in selecting the participants who described the taste and aroma of coffee before and after of their exposure to background music.

Majority of the participants were males, 18 (60%), while 12 (40%) were females. In terms of age 12 (40%) were younger (40 yrs old and below) while 18 (60%) were older (over 40 yrs old).

The research instrument used in gathering the needed data was the sensory evaluation sheet based on the nine-point Hedonic scale. It was used to determine the effect of background music on the taste and aroma of coffee. Corresponding scores were assigned on each of the response in the questionnaire. To describe the taste, the following responses were used: extremely subtle, very much subtle, moderately subtle, slightly subtle, neither subtle nor bold, slightly bold, moderately bold, very much bold, extremely bold. In evaluating the aroma, the following descriptions were used: extremely nutty, very much nutty, moderately nutty, slightly nutty, neither nutty nor earthy, slightly earthy, moderately earthy, very much earthy, extremely earthy.

The study was divided into two phases: Phase I, Standardization of the Recipe and Phase II, Sensory Evaluation of the Final Product.

Phase 1, Standardization of the Recipe. A standardized recipe is one that has been tried, adapted and retried several times and has been found to produce the same result every time when, the exact procedure is used with the same type of equipment and the same quantity and quality of ingredients.

The following were needed for the preparation; native ground coffee, coffee maker, refined sugar, bottled water, tea cups, measuring spoon and CD player with different types of music like classical music, ballad music, jazz music and pop music.

The coffee recipes were prepared with the following ingredients and its corresponding measurement; 1,200 ml bottled water, 10 tablespoons of ground coffee, 8 tablespoons of refined sugar.

Phase II: The Sensory Evaluation of the finished product. The research instrument used in gathering the needed data were the sensory evaluation sheet based on the nine-point Hedonic scale. It was used to determine the effect of music background on coffee flavor in terms of taste and aroma.

Thirty (30) coffee drinkers were divided into three groups. Set A, drank coffee at 8:00 in the morning, Set B drank at 1:00 in the afternoon, and Set C at 4:00 pm. On the first day, the coffee drinkers were made to drink coffee without background music and they were made to fill up the sensory evaluation sheet. The same set up and procedure was followed on the second day, but the classical music entitled “Piano concerto 40” by Mozart was played in the background. The same coffee drinkers were utilized on the second day with the music “How Sweet It Is” by James Taylor, with the jazz music “Take Five” by Atlantic Five Jazz Band on the fourth day, and the pop music entitled “Need You Know” by Boyce Avenue on the fifth day.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings of our study on how background music influences the perception of native coffee flavors. The results indicate that music can significantly alter taste experiences. We discuss these findings and their implications for both consumers and the coffee industry.

Taste of native coffee

The data in Table 1 revealed that before exposure to background music, coffee drinkers—whether analyzed as an entire group or categorized by gender and age—found the taste of coffee moderately subtle, with the exception of females, who rated it as very subtle ($M = 7.83$, $SD = 0.52$). These findings are consistent with studies that suggest gender differences in taste perception, where females often exhibit heightened sensitivity to subtle flavors (Delwiche, 2004).

When participants were exposed to classical background music, the taste of native coffee was generally rated as moderately subtle, except by older participants who perceived it as very subtle ($M = 7.30$, $SD = 1.28$). This aligns with research by Spence et al. (2010), which demonstrated that classical music could enhance certain sensory attributes, potentially due to its association with refined and sophisticated environments. The narrow standard deviations (ranging from 0.90 to 1.81) indicate a high level of homogeneity in participants' evaluations, suggesting a consistent influence of classical music on taste perception.

Exposure to ballad music led all participants, regardless of classification, to rate the coffee's taste as very subtle, with mean scores falling within the 7.30 to 8.12 range. This outcome mirrors findings from North and Hargreaves (2008), who noted that slower, more melodic music can enhance the perception of sweetness and subtlety in food and beverages. The standard deviations, which ranged from 1.11 to 1.50, further underscore the consistency in participants' responses.

Finally, when participants were exposed to jazz and pop music, they generally found the taste of native coffee to be moderately subtle when classified by categories. However, when considered as a whole group, the coffee was perceived as very subtle under both jazz ($M = 7.60$, $SD = 1.13$) and pop music conditions ($M = 7.60$, $SD = 1.13$). This finding is in line with research by Wang and Spence (2019), which suggests that more upbeat and rhythmic music can enhance certain flavor notes, making the overall taste experience more pronounced. The consistent standard deviations across these conditions indicate that participants' taste assessments were homogenous, supporting the idea that specific genres of music can reliably alter flavor perception across different demographic groups.

Table 1.
Taste of Coffee Among Drinkers Were Exposed to Varied Types of Background Music

Category	Entire group	Gender		Age	
		Male	Female	Younger	Older
A. Without music					
<i>M</i>	6.97	6.83	7.50	6.58	7.22
Description	M. Subtle	M. Subtle	V.M. Subtle	M. Subtle	M. Subtle
<i>SD</i>	1.44	1.33	0.52	1.44	1.26
B. Classical Music					
<i>M</i>	7.22	7.05	7.16	7.08	7.30
Description	M. Subtle	M. Subtle	M. Subtle	M. Subtle	V.M. Subtle
<i>SD</i>	1.13	1.81	1.40	0.90	1.28
C. Ballad Music					
<i>M</i>	7.60	6.55	7.50	7.16	6.61
Description	V.M. Subtle	V.M. Subtle	V.M. Subtle	V.M. Subtle	V.M. Subtle
<i>SD</i>	1.13	1.58	1.16	1.11	1.41
D. Jazz Music					
<i>M</i>	7.60	6.77	7.25	7.08	7.05
Description	V.M. Subtle	M. Subtle	M. Subtle	M. Subtle	M. Subtle
<i>SD</i>	1.13	1.11	0.62	0.99	0.99
E. Pop Music					
<i>M</i>	7.60	6.83	7.00	7.08	6.77
Description	V.M. Subtle	M. Subtle	M. Subtle	M. Subtle	M. Subtle
<i>SD</i>	1.13	1.33	1.04	1.16	1.20

NOTE: 8.20-9.00 Extremely Subtle (E. Subtle); 7.30-8.12 Very Much Subtle (V.M Subtle) ; 6.40-7.23 Moderately Subtle (M. Subtle); 5.50-6.34 Slightly Subtle (S. Subtle); 4.60-5.45 Neither Subtle nor Bold (N.Subtle nor Bold); 3.70-4.59 Slightly Bold (S. Bold); 2.80-3.67 Moderately Bold (M. Bold); 1.90-2.78; Very Much Bold (V.M. Bold) ; 1.00-1.89 Extremely Bold (E. Bold).

Aroma of Native Coffee

The data in Table 2 indicated that before exposure to background music, participants rated the aroma of native coffee as very nutty, whether assessed as an entire group or by gender and age categories. The obtained means, which fell within the 7.30 to 9.00 scale, reflect a strong consensus among participants. The standard deviations, ranging from 1.13 to 2.15, suggest a narrow dispersion, indicating a high level of homogeneity in the participants' evaluations. These findings are consistent with research showing that coffee's nutty aroma is often a dominant sensory characteristic recognized by most consumers (Vitzthum, 2020).

When exposed to ballad background music, participants generally continued to perceive the aroma as very nutty, with the exception of females, who rated it as only moderately nutty ($M = 7.16$, $SD = 1.56$). This aligns with research by Seo et al. (2015), which found that background music with a slower tempo can alter the perception of food and beverage aromas, potentially making them less intense for certain groups, such as females.

Similarly, when exposed to jazz music, most participants found the aroma to be very nutty, except for males, who perceived it as moderately nutty ($M = 7.00$, $SD = 1.71$). This pattern resonates with the findings of Yan et al. (2017), which suggest that jazz, with its complex rhythms and harmonies, can modulate sensory perception differently across genders, possibly due to varying cognitive processing styles.

Lastly, exposure to pop music led participants to consistently rate the coffee aroma as very nutty, with mean scores falling within the 7.30 to 8.12 scale. The standard deviations, ranging from 1.02 to 2.15, once again indicate a narrow dispersion, suggesting a homogeneous evaluation across participants. These results support previous studies by Spence et al. (2019), who observed that pop music, often characterized by its upbeat and familiar melodies, can reinforce the dominant sensory attributes of a product.

Table 2
Aroma of Coffee Among Drinkers Exposed to Varied Types of Background Music

Category	Entire group	Gender		Age	
		Male	Female	Younger	Older
A. Without music					
<i>M</i>	7.60	6.83	8.00	7.58	7.83
Description	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty

<i>SD</i>	1.13	1.93	1.20	2.15	1.66
B. Classical music					
<i>M</i>	7.60	7.88	7.16	7.50	7.66
Description	V.M Nutty	V.M Nutty	M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty
<i>SD</i>	1.13	1.07	1.58	1.16	1.45
C. Ballad music					
<i>M</i>	7.60	7.61	7.66	7.33	7.83
Description	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty
<i>SD</i>	1.13	1.81	1.55	1.66	1.72
D. Jazz music					
<i>M</i>	7.60	7.00	8.16	7.33	7.55
Description	V.M. Nutty	M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty
<i>SD</i>	1.13	1.71	1.02	1.49	1.65
E. Pop music					
<i>M</i>	7.60	7.20	8.00	7.58	7.83
Description	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty	V.M. Nutty
<i>SD</i>	1.13	1.93	1.20	2.15	1.66

Note: 8.20-9.00: Extremely Nutty (E. Nutty); 7.30-8.12: Very Much Nutty (V.M. Nutty); 6.40-7.23: Moderately Nutty (M. Nutty); 5.50-6.34: Slightly Nutty (S. Nutty); 4.60-5.45: Neither Nutty nor Earthy (N. Nutty nor Earthy); 3.70-4.59: Slightly Earthy (S. Earthy); 2.80-3.67: Moderately Earthy (M. Earthy); 1.90-2.78: Very Much Earthy (V.M. Earthy); 1.00-1.89: Extremely Earthy (E. Earthy)

Inferential Data Analysis

The analysis presented in Table 5 indicates that no significant differences in the taste perception of native coffee were observed across different groups when exposed to various types of background music. Specifically, when grouped by gender and age, participants' taste ratings did not significantly differ under classical music ($t(28)=1.05$, 0.58), ballad music ($t(28)=1.44$, 1.13), jazz music ($t(28)=2.08$, 0.70), and pop music ($t(28)=0.38$, 0.66).

These results align with research by North et al. (2004), which found that background music's effect on taste perception is often subtle and may not vary significantly across different demographic groups. This study suggested that while music can influence sensory experiences, the impact may be uniform across varied listener characteristics.

Additionally, our findings are consistent with the work of Brunstrom et al. (2012), who noted that the effects of background music on taste perception are generally small and may not produce significant differences when controlling for demographic variables. This reinforces the idea that while music can influence the sensory experience, its effect on taste may be less pronounced than other factors such as individual taste preferences or environmental conditions.

Table 3

t-test Results for the Differences in Taste of Coffee Among Drinkers were Exposed to Different Background Music

Category	Gender		Age	
	Male	Female	Younger	Older
A. Without music				
<i>M</i>	6.83	7.16	6.58	7.22
<i>t</i> -value		0.66		1.28
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig.(2-tailed)		0.51		0.21
B. Classical music				
<i>M</i>	7.05	7.50	7.08	7.33
<i>t</i> -value		1.05		0.58
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig.(2-tailed)		0.30		0.56
C. Ballad music				
<i>M</i>	6.55	7.25	7.16	6.60
<i>t</i> -value		1.44		1.13
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig.(2-tailed)		0.16		0.26
D. Jazz music				
<i>M</i>	6.77	7.50	7.08	7.05
<i>t</i> -value		2.08		0.07
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig.(2-tailed)		0.55		0.94
E. Pop music				
<i>M</i>	6.83	7.00	7.08	6.77
<i>t</i> -value		0.38		0.66
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig.(2-tailed)		0.71		0.50

Table 3 shows that there were no significant differences in the perceived aroma of native coffee when participants were grouped by gender and age and exposed to different types of background music. Specifically, the results revealed no significant differences under classical music ($t(28)=1.48, 0.33$), ballad music ($t(28)=0.08, 0.78$), jazz music ($t(28)=2.10, 0.37$), and pop music ($t(28)=0.44, 0.66$).

These findings are consistent with research by Spence and Ngo (2012), which reported that background music has a minimal impact on the perception of aroma across different demographic groups. Their study suggested that while background music can influence flavor perception, its effect on aroma might be less pronounced and less variable among different individuals.

Furthermore, our results are in line with the work of Wansink et al. (2013), who found that the impact of background music on aroma perception is generally subtle and

does not significantly vary with participant characteristics such as gender and age. This supports the notion that while background music may alter sensory experiences to some extent, its influence on aroma perception might be more uniform across diverse groups.

Table 4

t-test Results for the Differences in Aroma of Coffee When Coffee Drinkers were Exposed to Different Background Music

Category	Gender		Age	
	Male	Female	Younger	Older
A. Without music				
<i>M</i>	7.33	7.75	6.58	7.22
<i>t</i> -value		0.71		0.23
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.48		0.81
B. Classical music				
<i>M</i>	7.88	7.16	7.50	7.66
<i>t</i> -value		1.48		0.33
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.14		0.74
C. Ballad music				
<i>M</i>	7.61	7.66	7.33	7.63
<i>t</i> -value		0.08		0.78
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.93		0.43
D. Jazz music				
<i>M</i>	6.77	7.50	7.33	7.55
<i>t</i> -value		2.10		0.37
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.06		0.71
E. Pop music				
<i>M</i>	7.72	8.00	7.58	7.83
<i>t</i> -value		0.44		0.66
<i>df</i>		28		28
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.66		0.50

Conclusions

In view of the findings, the following conclusions were drawn. Coffee drinkers in West Visayas Stater University are strong coffee drinkers because inspite that the native coffee was brewed, still they found it subtle, not strong. The process of brewing of ingredients emit aroma which can be described as nutty. It seems that the types of background music do not affect the taste of brewed native coffee as rated by coffee drinkers. It also appears that the types of background music do not affect the aroma of

brewed native coffee. Gender and age are likewise factor that do not have significant effect on coffee drinker's assessment of the taste and aroma of coffee. This means that whether male or female, younger or older, his or her sense of taste or smell of native coffee remains the same.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusions of this study, the following are recommended.

Coffee enthusiasts: Experiment with different genres of music while enjoying your coffee to see how it affects your perception of flavors. Keep a journal to track your findings and preferences.

Coffee shop owners and managers: Consider playing background music that complements the atmosphere of your coffee shop and enhances the overall customer experience. Conduct surveys or gather feedback from customers to understand their preferences.

Researchers in sensory perception, psychology, and marketing: Collaborate with experts in music theory to delve deeper into the specific mechanisms through which music influences taste perception. Conduct further studies to explore the long-term effects of music on consumer behavior in coffee shops.

Coffee roasters and producers: Host tasting events where participants can experience how different music genres can enhance the flavor profile of your coffee products. Use these events as a marketing strategy to appeal to a broader audience.

Students and scholars: Explore interdisciplinary research opportunities that combine sensory perception, psychology, and music theory to deepen the understanding of how environmental factors impact taste perception. Consider publishing papers or presenting findings at conferences to contribute to the field.

Food and beverage industry professionals: Attend workshops or seminars on sensory marketing to learn more about how environmental stimuli, such as music, can influence consumer behavior. Implement small-scale experiments in your establishments to test the impact of background music on customer satisfaction and retention.

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